

Thessaloniki, 15/01/2026

RAISE Selected as CORDIS “Project of the Month” for January 2026

European Commission feature spotlights RAISE’s secure “data visiting” approach and key project results enabling trustworthy, FAIR-aligned data processing

RAISE consortium is proud to announce that the project has been selected as CORDIS “Project of the Month” (January 2026). Awarded by the European Commission’s CORDIS platform for EU-funded research and innovation, this distinction is a major visibility milestone that underscores the **relevance, maturity, and impact potential** of RAISE outcomes.

In its feature, CORDIS highlights a core challenge for today’s research community: researchers’ justified reluctance to make data publicly accessible, particularly when datasets are sensitive and data-use control, recognition, and compliance are critical. RAISE addresses this by shifting from traditional “data sharing” to “**data visiting**”: data providers keep datasets within their own infrastructure and retain control and ownership, while authorised users **execute algorithms in trusted environments** rather than downloading data.

The CORDIS article also emphasises how the [RAISE Portal](#) records data processing and provides a persistent **Research Analysis Identifier (RAI)**, to support **reproducibility** and ensure **traceability, attribution, and compliance** with sensitive-data regulations. This approach strengthens accountability for all parties involved and helps ensure that research data and research work are properly recognised.

Project results highlighted through RAISE outcomes

RAISE’s recognition as “Project of the Month” reflects the project’s progress in delivering concrete, interoperable building blocks/components that make controlled, trustworthy research data processing possible at scale. In particular, RAISE has developed and advanced:

- **A trustworthy network of RAI-certified nodes** providing storage and processing resources for distributed, crowdsourced execution.
- The **RAI Cloud platform** to orchestrate dataset discovery, access, and processing across participating environments.
- The **Research Analysis Identifier (RAI)**, linking results with dataset information and processing scripts to support verifiability and reuse without exposing raw data.
- **Trust services**, including dataset proof-of-origin and plagiarism-identification capabilities to reinforce confidence in research outputs.
- **A synthetic data generator**, supporting testing, development, and broader reuse where direct data access is constrained.

As **Asst. Prof. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, RAISE Project Coordinator** at the Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, noted, “*Being recognised by CORDIS as Project of the Month underscores the need for practical solutions and confirms that RAISE outcomes are well accepted by the scientific community.*”. **Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis, RAISE Scientific Coordinator** (Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) highlights that “*This momentum will continue through [RAISE Suite](#), the project’s continuation.*” Reflecting this progress, the CORDIS feature also points to key milestones such as the launch of the RAISE Portal, and the creation of a spin-off company ([XEETI](#)) focused on blockchain and AI technologies, alongside growing interest from organisations beyond the Open Science community in exploring RAISE services and their value.

Read the CORDIS Feature:

[RAISE: Technology for a more transparent approach to sharing, visiting and processing data](#)

Available at: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058479/news>

About RAISE

RAISE (Research Analysis Identifier System) (Grant agreement ID: 101058479) is an EU-funded project advancing secure, transparent, and FAIR-aligned ways to access and process research data, particularly sensitive datasets, by enabling “data visiting” in trusted environments and strengthening traceability and reproducibility of data-driven research.

More information on RAISE Science project can be found here: <https://raise-science.eu/>

Consortium

- ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS, LAB OF MEDICAL PHYSICS AND DIGITAL INNOVATION (AUTH)
- FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH (VICOM)
- NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT (INTRA)
- PANEPISTIMIO DYTIKIS MAKEDONIAS (UOWM)
- UNIVERSITY OF MACEDONIA (UOM)
- TECREANDO B.V. (TECREANDO)
- XEETI (XEETI)
- ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS (CERTH)
- INNOV-ACTS LIMITED (INNOV-ACTS)
- VILABS LTD (VILABS)
- PC KYKLIKI VELTISTOPOIISI IKE (Cyclopt)
- KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET SE (KI)
- ATHINA-EREVNITIKO KENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS (ATHENA)
- AINIGMA TECHNOLOGIES (AINIGMA)
- UNIVERSITEIT HASSELT (UHASSELT)
- OPENAIRE AMKE (OPENAIRE)
- CENTRO EUROPEO DI FORMAZIONE ERICERCA IN INGEGNERIA SISMICA (EUCENTRE)
- ENVE.X SINGLE MEMBER PC (ENVE.X)
- UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON (SOTON)
- ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSIT (McGill)

Key facts

 Start:
1st October 2022

 Duration:
40 months

 Budget:
€4,836,125.00

 Consortium:
20 partners

Project coordinator:

Asst. Prof. **Evdokimos Konstantinidis**, Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Scientific coordinator:

Prof. **Panagiotis Bamidis**, Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

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